

LAMPIRAN 2

HASIL KUESIONER PRE DESIGN

Tampilan komputer HMI SAS dapat merepresentasikan tata letak peralatan secara umum

7 jawaban

Bentuk icon / simbol mudah dimengerti (mengacu kepada peralatan spesifik tertentu)

7 jawaban

Kemudahan dalam mengenali informasi status peralatan (Open / Close)

7 jawaban

Kemudahan dalam mencari informasi data pengukuran real time yang relevan dengan proses pencatatan logsheet (Tegangan / Arus / Daya / Frekuensi)

7 jawaban

Status Peralatan dalam kondisi (bertegangan atau tidak bertegangan) dapat mudah dipahami

7 jawaban

Operator dapat melaksanakan kegiatan pengoperasian peralatan melalui HMI tanpa harus menuju ke panel kontrol

7 jawaban

Pengukuran dapat tercatat secara otomatis dan dapat diarsipkan sesuai kebutuhan

7 jawaban

Rekaman unusual event dan trip dapat terekam sesuai kebutuhan

7 jawaban

Operator dapat mengetahui anomali / ketidaknormalan gangguan peralatan secara real time

7 jawaban

Operator dapat mengetahui anomali / ketidaknormalan gangguan peralatan secara real time

7 jawaban

Sistem SAS tetap dapat dioperasikan ketika dalam kondisi urgent (GI Ende Black Out atau hilang tegangan)

7 jawaban

Terdapat contingency plan apabila pengoperasian peralatan via Sistem SAS mengalami kegagalan akibat faktor teknis maupun non teknis

7 jawaban

LAMPIRAN 3

HASIL KUESIONER POST DESIGN

Saya pikir bahwa saya akan membutuhkan bantuan dari orang teknis untuk dapat menggunakan sistem SAS ini

 Copy

7 responses

Saya menemukan berbagai fungsi di sistem ini telah diintegrasikan dengan baik

 Copy

7 responses

Saya pikir ada terlalu banyak ketidakkonsistenan dalam sistem ini

 Copy

7 responses

Saya membayangkan bahwa kebanyakan orang akan mudah untuk mempelajari aplikasi ini dengan sangat cepat

 Copy

7 responses

Saya menemukan, aplikasi ini sangat rumit untuk digunakan

 Copy

7 responses

Saya merasa sangat percaya diri untuk menggunakan aplikasi ini

 Copy

7 responses

LAMPIRAN 4

HASIL UJI VALIDITAS

		Correlations									
		Item01	Item02	Item03	Item04	Item05	Item06	Item07	Item08	Item09	TotalScore
Item01	Pearson Correlation	1	1.000**	1.000**	1.000**	1.000**	1.000**	1.000**	1.000**	1.000**	1.000**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		<.001	<.001	<.001	<.001	<.001	<.001	<.001	<.001	<.001
	N	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7
Item02	Pearson Correlation	1.000**	1	1.000**	1.000**	1.000**	1.000**	1.000**	1.000**	1.000**	1.000**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	<.001		<.001	<.001	<.001	<.001	<.001	<.001	<.001	<.001
	N	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7
Item03	Pearson Correlation	1.000**	1.000**	1	1.000**	1.000**	1.000**	1.000**	1.000**	1.000**	1.000**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	<.001	<.001		<.001	<.001	<.001	<.001	<.001	<.001	<.001
	N	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7
Item04	Pearson Correlation	1.000**	1.000**	1.000**	1	1.000**	1.000**	1.000**	1.000**	1.000**	1.000**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	<.001	<.001	<.001		<.001	<.001	<.001	<.001	<.001	<.001
	N	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7
Item05	Pearson Correlation	1.000**	1.000**	1.000**	1.000**	1	1.000**	1.000**	1.000**	1.000**	1.000**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	<.001	<.001	<.001	<.001		<.001	<.001	<.001	<.001	<.001
	N	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7
Item06	Pearson Correlation	1.000**	1.000**	1.000**	1.000**	1.000**	1	1.000**	1.000**	1.000**	1.000**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	<.001	<.001	<.001	<.001	<.001		<.001	<.001	<.001	<.001
	N	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7
Item07	Pearson Correlation	1.000**	1.000**	1.000**	1.000**	1.000**	1.000**	1	1.000**	1.000**	1.000**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	<.001	<.001	<.001	<.001	<.001	<.001		<.001	<.001	<.001
	N	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7
Item08	Pearson Correlation	1.000**	1.000**	1.000**	1.000**	1.000**	1.000**	1.000**	1	1.000**	1.000**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	<.001	<.001	<.001	<.001	<.001	<.001	<.001		<.001	<.001
	N	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7
Item09	Pearson Correlation	1.000**	1.000**	1.000**	1.000**	1.000**	1.000**	1.000**	1.000**	1	1.000**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	<.001	<.001	<.001	<.001	<.001	<.001	<.001	<.001		<.001
	N	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7
TotalScore	Pearson Correlation	1.000**	1.000**	1.000**	1.000**	1.000**	1.000**	1.000**	1.000**	1.000**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	<.001	<.001	<.001	<.001	<.001	<.001	<.001	<.001	<.001	
	N	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

LAMPIRAN 5
PROSES UJI RELIABILITAS KUESIONER *PRE-DESIGN*

❖ **STEP 1**

Melakukan penghitungan *Cronbach Alpha* dengan N of Items 12 menggunakan fitur *Reliability Analysis* pada *Software IBM SPSS Statistics Data Editor* dan didapatkan hasil sebagai berikut:

Case Processing Summary

		N	%
Cases	Valid	7	100.0
	Excluded ^a	0	.0
	Total	7	100.0

a. Listwise deletion based on all variables in the procedure.

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.991	12

Item-Total Statistics

	Scale Mean if Item Deleted	Scale Variance if Item Deleted	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
Item01	49.86	31.143	.982	.989
Item02	49.86	31.143	.982	.989
Item03	49.86	31.143	.982	.989
Item04	49.86	31.143	.982	.989
Item05	49.86	31.143	.982	.989
Item06	49.86	31.143	.982	.989
Item07	49.86	31.143	.982	.989
Item08	49.86	31.143	.982	.989
Item09	49.86	31.143	.982	.989
Item10	50.00	32.000	.827	.992
Item11	50.00	32.000	.827	.992
Item12	50.00	32.000	.827	.992

❖ **STEP 2**

Melakukan eliminasi pada **Item 11** yang memiliki nilai *Cronbach' Alpha* = 0.992 (lebih besar dari nilai *Cronbach' Alpha* dengan N of Items 12 = 0.991 sesuai dengan hasil **STEP 1**). Sehingga didapatkan hasil sebagai berikut :

Case Processing Summary

		N	%
Cases	Valid	7	100.0
	Excluded ^a	0	.0
	Total	7	100.0

a. Listwise deletion based on all variables in the procedure.

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.992	11

Item-Total Statistics

	Scale Mean if Item Deleted	Scale Variance if Item Deleted	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
Item01	45.43	26.286	.990	.990
Item02	45.43	26.286	.990	.990
Item03	45.43	26.286	.990	.990
Item04	45.43	26.286	.990	.990
Item05	45.43	26.286	.990	.990
Item06	45.43	26.286	.990	.990
Item07	45.43	26.286	.990	.990
Item08	45.43	26.286	.990	.990
Item09	45.43	26.286	.990	.990
Item10	45.57	27.286	.793	.995
Item12	45.57	27.286	.793	.995

❖ **STEP 3**

Melakukan eliminasi pada **Item 12** yang memiliki nilai *Cronbach'Alpha* = 0.995 (lebih besar dari nilai *Cronbach'Alpha* dengan N of Items 11 = 0.992 sesuai dengan hasil **STEP 2**). Sehingga didapatkan hasil sebagai berikut :

Case Processing Summary

		N	%
Cases	Valid	7	100.0
	Excluded ^a	0	.0
	Total	7	100.0

a. Listwise deletion based on all variables in the procedure.

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.995	10

Item-Total Statistics

	Scale Mean if Item Deleted	Scale Variance if Item Deleted	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
Item01	41.00	22.000	.997	.994
Item02	41.00	22.000	.997	.994
Item03	41.00	22.000	.997	.994
Item04	41.00	22.000	.997	.994
Item05	41.00	22.000	.997	.994
Item06	41.00	22.000	.997	.994
Item07	41.00	22.000	.997	.994
Item08	41.00	22.000	.997	.994
Item09	41.00	22.000	.997	.994
Item10	41.14	23.143	.750	1.000

❖ **STEP 4**

Melakukan eliminasi pada **Item 10** yang memiliki nilai *Cronbach' Alpha* = 1.000 (lebih besar dari nilai *Cronbach' Alpha* dengan N of Items 10 = 0.995 sesuai dengan hasil **STEP 3**). Sehingga didapatkan hasil sebagai berikut :

Case Processing Summary

		N	%
Cases	Valid	7	100.0
	Excluded ^a	0	.0
	Total	7	100.0

a. Listwise deletion based on all variables in the procedure.

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.995	10

Item-Total Statistics

	Scale Mean if Item Deleted	Scale Variance if Item Deleted	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
Item01	41.00	22.000	.997	.994
Item02	41.00	22.000	.997	.994
Item03	41.00	22.000	.997	.994
Item04	41.00	22.000	.997	.994
Item05	41.00	22.000	.997	.994
Item06	41.00	22.000	.997	.994
Item07	41.00	22.000	.997	.994
Item08	41.00	22.000	.997	.994
Item09	41.00	22.000	.997	.994
Item10	41.14	23.143	.750	1.000

❖ **STEP 5**

- Berdasarkan hasil **STEP 4**, 9 item yang tersisa telah dikatakan *reliable* karena nilai *Cronbach' Alpha* untuk setiap item telah bernilai kurang dari atau sama dengan (\leq) nilai *Cronbach' Alpha* dengan N of Items 9 = 1.00.

Case Processing Summary

		N	%
Cases	Valid	7	100.0
	Excluded ^a	0	.0
	Total	7	100.0

a. Listwise deletion based on all variables in the procedure.

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
1.000	9

Item-Total Statistics

	Scale Mean if Item Deleted	Scale Variance if Item Deleted	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
Item01	36.57	18.286	1.000	1.000
Item02	36.57	18.286	1.000	1.000
Item03	36.57	18.286	1.000	1.000
Item04	36.57	18.286	1.000	1.000
Item05	36.57	18.286	1.000	1.000
Item06	36.57	18.286	1.000	1.000
Item07	36.57	18.286	1.000	1.000
Item08	36.57	18.286	1.000	1.000
Item09	36.57	18.286	1.000	1.000

- Dari 12 Item yang dilakukan uji reliabilitas, didapatkan hanya 9 Item yang dapat dipertanggungjawabkan (dapat disebar ke populasi)

LAMPIRAN 6

Teleinformasi Data untuk Konfigurasi Umum pada Gardu Induk *Double Busbar*

Group Bay	Fungsi	Jenis Teleinformasi	Tipe	Keterangan
Gardu Induk (General)	Frekuensi	Telemetry	Value Display	<i>Displays the measurement value (real time)</i>
	Communication Alarm	Telesignal	Alarm	<i>Annunciation of abnormal condition (audible alarm, flashing display, etc)</i>
	Protection Faulty	Telesignal	Alarm	<i>Annunciation of abnormal condition (audible alarm, flashing display, etc)</i>
	Peripheral Alarm	Telesignal	Alarm	<i>Annunciation of abnormal condition (audible alarm, flashing display, etc)</i>
	RTU Alarm	Telesignal	Alarm	<i>Annunciation of abnormal condition (audible alarm, flashing display, etc)</i>
	Synchronizing Failure	Telesignal	Alarm	<i>Annunciation of abnormal condition (audible alarm, flashing display, etc)</i>
	VAC Supply Failure	Telesignal	Alarm	<i>Annunciation of abnormal condition (audible alarm, flashing display, etc)</i>
	VDC Supply Failure	Telesignal	Alarm	<i>Annunciation of abnormal condition (audible alarm, flashing display, etc)</i>
	Software Interlocking Bypass	Telesignal	Alarm	<i>Annunciation of abnormal condition (audible alarm, flashing display, etc)</i>
	IED Faulty	Telesignal	Alarm	<i>Annunciation of abnormal condition (audible alarm, flashing display, etc)</i>
	Switch On to Fault	Telesignal	Alarm	<i>Annunciation of abnormal condition (audible alarm, flashing display, etc)</i>
	Master Trip Operate	Telesignal	Alarm	<i>Annunciation of abnormal condition (audible alarm, flashing display, etc)</i>
	Control Disable Switch	Telesignal	Indication	<i>Event / Indication (normal condition)</i>
	Check Synchronizing Override	Telesignal	Indication	<i>Event / Indication (normal condition)</i>
	Dummy Breaker Closed / Opened	Telesignal	Indication	<i>Event / Indication (normal condition)</i>
	Local Remote	Telesignal	Indication	<i>Event / Indication (normal condition)</i>
	Check Synchronizing Override	Telecontrol	Control	<i>Execute Triggers to change equipment status</i>
	Dummy Breaker Closed / Opened	Telecontrol	Control	<i>Execute Triggers to change equipment status</i>
Bay Kopel 70 kV	Tegangan	Telemetry	Value Display	<i>Displays the measurement value (real time)</i>
	Bay Fault DC	Telesignal	Alarm	<i>Annunciation of abnormal condition (audible alarm, flashing display, etc)</i>
	Over Voltage Relay Operate	Telesignal	Alarm	<i>Annunciation of abnormal condition (audible alarm, flashing display, etc)</i>
	Busbar Protection	Telesignal	Alarm	<i>Annunciation of abnormal condition (audible alarm, flashing display, etc)</i>
	Under Voltage Relay	Telesignal	Alarm	<i>Annunciation of abnormal condition (audible alarm, flashing display, etc)</i>
	Voltage Status	Telesignal	Alarm	<i>Annunciation of abnormal condition (audible alarm, flashing display, etc)</i>

Group Bay	Fungsi	Jenis Teleinformasi	Tipe	Keterangan
Bay Transmisi 70 kV	Arus	Telemetry	Value Display	<i>Displays the measurement value (real time)</i>
	Daya Aktif	Telemetry	Value Display	<i>Displays the measurement value (real time)</i>
	Daya Reaktif	Telemetry	Value Display	<i>Displays the measurement value (real time)</i>
	Tegangan	Telemetry	Value Display	<i>Displays the measurement value (real time)</i>
	Circuit Breaker Auto Reclose	Telesignal	Indication	<i>Event / Indication (normal condition)</i>
	Auto Reclose On / Off	Telesignal	Indication	<i>Event / Indication (normal condition)</i>
	Bay Fault DC	Telesignal	Alarm	<i>Annunciation of abnormal condition (audible alarm, flashing display, etc)</i>
	Breaker Fault	Telesignal	Alarm	<i>Annunciation of abnormal condition (audible alarm, flashing display, etc)</i>
	Circuit Breaker Trip	Telesignal	Alarm	<i>Annunciation of abnormal condition (audible alarm, flashing display, etc)</i>
	Check Synchronizing In Progress	Telesignal	Indication	<i>Event / Indication (normal condition)</i>
	Current Differential	Telesignal	Alarm	<i>Annunciation of abnormal condition (audible alarm, flashing display, etc)</i>
	Directional Earth Fault	Telesignal	Alarm	<i>Annunciation of abnormal condition (audible alarm, flashing display, etc)</i>
	Distance Zone 1	Telesignal	Alarm	<i>Annunciation of abnormal condition (audible alarm, flashing display, etc)</i>
	Distance Zone 2	Telesignal	Alarm	<i>Annunciation of abnormal condition (audible alarm, flashing display, etc)</i>
	Distance Zone 3	Telesignal	Alarm	<i>Annunciation of abnormal condition (audible alarm, flashing display, etc)</i>
	Ground Fault Relay	Telesignal	Alarm	<i>Annunciation of abnormal condition (audible alarm, flashing display, etc)</i>
	Over Current Relay	Telesignal	Alarm	<i>Annunciation of abnormal condition (audible alarm, flashing display, etc)</i>
	Direct Transfer Trip	Telesignal	Alarm	<i>Annunciation of abnormal condition (audible alarm, flashing display, etc)</i>
	Teleprotection Trip Receive	Telesignal	Indication	<i>Event / Indication (normal condition)</i>
	Teleprotection Trip Transmit	Telesignal	Indication	<i>Event / Indication (normal condition)</i>
	Bus Isolator Switch	Telesignal	Indication	<i>Event / Indication (normal condition)</i>
	Circuit Brekaer Closed / Opened	Telesignal	Indication	<i>Event / Indication (normal condition)</i>
	Check Synchronizing Override	Telesignal	Indication	<i>Event / Indication (normal condition)</i>
	Line Isolator Switch Close / Opened	Telesignal	Indication	<i>Event / Indication (normal condition)</i>
	Local Remote	Telesignal	Indication	<i>Event / Indication (normal condition)</i>
	Bus Isolator Switch	Telecontrol	Control	<i>Execute Triggers to change equipment status</i>
	Breaker Close / Opened	Telecontrol	Control	<i>Execute Triggers to change equipment status</i>

Group Bay	Fungsi	Jenis Teleinformasi	Tipe	Keterangan
Bay Trafo Tenaga	Daya Aktif	Telemetry	Value Display	<i>Displays the measurement value (real time)</i>
	Daya Reaktif	Telemetry	Value Display	<i>Displays the measurement value (real time)</i>
	Bay Fault DC	Telesignal	Alarm	<i>Annunciation of abnormal condition (audible alarm, flashing display, etc)</i>
	Breaker Fault	Telesignal	Alarm	<i>Annunciation of abnormal condition (audible alarm, flashing display, etc)</i>
	Circuit Breaker Trip	Telesignal	Alarm	<i>Annunciation of abnormal condition (audible alarm, flashing display, etc)</i>
	Differential	Telesignal	Alarm	<i>Annunciation of abnormal condition (audible alarm, flashing display, etc)</i>
	Restricted Earth Fault	Telesignal	Alarm	<i>Annunciation of abnormal condition (audible alarm, flashing display, etc)</i>
	Ground Fault Relay	Telesignal	Alarm	<i>Annunciation of abnormal condition (audible alarm, flashing display, etc)</i>
	Over Current Relay	Telesignal	Alarm	<i>Annunciation of abnormal condition (audible alarm, flashing display, etc)</i>
	Temperature Alarm	Telesignal	Alarm	<i>Annunciation of abnormal condition (audible alarm, flashing display, etc)</i>
	Temperature Trip	Telesignal	Alarm	<i>Annunciation of abnormal condition (audible alarm, flashing display, etc)</i>
	Transformer Alarm	Telesignal	Alarm	<i>Annunciation of abnormal condition (audible alarm, flashing display, etc)</i>
	Transformer Trip	Telesignal	Alarm	<i>Annunciation of abnormal condition (audible alarm, flashing display, etc)</i>
	Bus Isolator Switch	Telesignal	Indication	<i>Event / Indication (normal condition)</i>
	Circuit Breaker Closed / Opened	Telesignal	Indication	<i>Event / Indication (normal condition)</i>
	Local Remote	Telesignal	Indication	<i>Event / Indication (normal condition)</i>
	Bus Isolator Switch	Telecontrol	Control	<i>Execute Triggers to change equipment status</i>
	Circuit Breaker Closed / Opened	Telecontrol	Control	<i>Execute Triggers to change equipment status</i>

LAMPIRAN 7
KETENTUAN DRAWING SIMBOL (SPLN S5.001:2008)

SIMBOL GAMBAR

	Trafo Daya Dua Belitan		
	Trafo Daya Tiga Belitan		
	Cut out fuse		
	Pemutus Balik Otomatis	I	Arus
	Load Break Switch	V	Tegangan
	Isolating Switch (Disconnecting Switch)	F	Frekuensi
	Earthing Switch	P	Daya aktif
	Surge / Lightning Arrester	Q	Daya reaktif
	Current Transformer (3phases)	TPI	Tap Position Indication
	Voltage Transformer	RCD	Remote Control Digital
	Reaktor	RCA	Remote Control Analog
	Kapasitor	TSS	Telesignal Single
	Capacitor Voltage Transformer	TSS	Telesignal Double
	Gardu Distribusi	L/R	Local/ Remote
		LFC(P₀ Pr, N)	Load Frequency Control

LAMPIRAN 8
KETENTUAN TAMPILAN STATUS (SPLN S5.001:2008)

ITEMS	SYMBOL	REMARK
CB CLOSED		Busbars color, filled
CB OPENED		Busbars color, blank
PBO CLOSED		Feeder's color filled
PBO OPENED		Feeder's color blank
LBS CLOSED		Feeder's color
LBS OPENED		Feeder's color
DS CLOSED		Feeder's color filled
DS OPENED		Feeder's color blank
ES CLOSED		Feeder's color
ES OPENED		Feeder's color
RACKED IN CB CLOSED		Feeder's color filled
RACKED IN CB OPENED		Feeder's color blank
RACKED OUT CB CLOSED		Feeder's color filled
RACKED OUT CB OPENED		Feeder's color blank
GARDU PORTAL TIANG		Feeder's color
GARDU TEMBOK/BESI		Feeder's color
CUT OUT FUSE		Feeder's color
GENERATOR		Feeder's color
TRANSF 2 WINDINGS		Feeder's color
TRANSF 3 WINDINGS		Feeder's color
REACTOR		Feeder's color
CAPACITOR		Feeder's color
VOLTAGE STATUS:		
	LIVE	
	DEAD	

LAMPIRAN 9
KETENTUAN WARNA TAMPILAN (SPLN S5.001:2008)

URAIAN	WARNA
Single line diagram 500 kV	Biru
Single line diagram 275 kV	Biru-muda
Single line diagram 150 kV	Merah
Single line diagram 70 kV	Kuning
Single line diagram 30 kV	Hijau
Single line diagram 20 kV	Coklat
Single line diagram 12 kV	Abu-abu
Single line diagram 6 kV	Merah muda
Single line diagram 0.4 kV	Hijau-muda
All devices	Warna Busbar
Invalid device	Ungu dan perubahan simbol
Device saat loss connection (RTU out of poll)	Oranye
Background color	Hitam
Ground color	Biru-tua
Kondisi tidak bertegangan	Putih
Perubahan status karena gangguan	Frame CB warna merah, <i>blinking</i>
Perubahan status karena local dari gardu induk	Warna Busbar, <i>blinking</i> + karakter "L"
Perubahan status karena remote dari dispatcher	Warna Busbar, <i>blinking</i>
Telemetering	Putih
Invalid telemetering	Ungu
Telesignal Alarm	Warna kuning, <i>blinking</i>

Keterangan:

- Untuk change of state gangguan, setelah acknowledge *blinking* hilang, warna merah pada frame CB mengikuti warna busbar.
- Untuk level tegangan yang tidak tercantum dalam tabel di atas, menggunakan warna pada single line diagram level tegangan terdekat.
- Warna jaringan sesuai dengan *feeder colouring*.
- Untuk detail kode warna akan dijelaskan pada SPLN mengenai kode simbol dan warna.

LAMPIRAN 10

LOGSHEET MANUAL GI 70 kV ENDE

PT. PLN (PERSERO) WILAYAH NTT UPK NUSA TENGGARA TIMUR ULTA FLORES GARDU INDUK ENDE		SISTEM MANAJEMEN TERINTEGRASI UNIT TRANSMISI DAN GARDU INDUK															NO. DOKUMEN					
		LOGSHEET PENYULANG 70 KV GI ENDE															REVISI	TANGGAL	HALAMAN			
Hari/Tanggal : Minggu, 30 Juli 2023																						
JAM	ROPA I						AMPERE			ROPA II						AMPERE						
	RS	ST	TR	RN	SN	TN	KW	KVAR	R	S	T	RS	ST	TR	RN	SN	TN	KW	KVAR	R	S	T
00.00	66	66	66	37	37	37	5985	1120	46,3	48,7	49,8	66	66	66	37	37	37	252	1288	10,9	11,6	10
01.00							-5.600	1085	43,3	45,5	46,5							-106	-1204	10,3	10,9	10,52
02.00							-5.650	1085	42,9	45,1	46,0							-168	-1190	10,19	10,8	10,16
03.00							-5.495	1085	42,7	45,1	46,2							0,1	-1232	10,2	11,0	10,63
04.00							-5.600	1155	45,4	45,7	46,7							560	-1204	10,3	10,7	10,36
05.00							-5.565	1155	43,2	45,6	46,7							280	-1222	10,2	10,9	10,32
06.00							-5.605	1082	43,8	46,2	47,1							-168	-1204	10,2	10,7	10,20
07.00							-5.495	1015	47,7	45,3	46,2							112	-1456	11,8	12,6	11,5
08.00							55,20	340	47,7	45,3	46,2							000,7	1700	13,0	14,2	13,7
09.00							54,95	340	42,3	45,2	46,2							220	1792	14,6	15,4	15,8
10.00							60,25	660	46,4	49,3	50,3							1030	1820	17,5	18,1	18,9
11.00							60,70	865	49,1	50,6	51,3							920	1904	17,8	18,3	18,6
12.00							61,60	865	43,8	46,1	46,9							320	1932	17,2	17,9	18,5
13.00							56,85	865	43,3	44,1	44,9							280	1904	16,4	16,6	16,5
14.00							52,85	865	40,6	45,1	46,1							280	1904	15,8	16,4	16,5
15.00							57,05	700	43,9	46,6	47,6							350	1960	16,2	17,1	17,8
16.00							53,15	770	45,8	48,7	49,6							370	1960	16,2	17,4	18,1
17.00							5.460	770	42,2	40,7	46,0							260,5	1900	16,7	17,5	18,1
18.00							6.430	840	42,7	40,7	46,0							220,3	-1456	11,8	12,6	12,1
19.00							7.495	840	42,7	40,7	46,0							220,3	-1204	10,2	10,7	10,2
20.00							7.475	840	42,7	40,7	46,0							220,3	-1204	10,2	10,7	10,2
21.00							6.490	1000	42,6	40,6	46,0							120,3	-1204	10,2	10,7	10,2
22.00							6.440	1000	40,3	42,6	43,5							120,3	-1204	10,2	10,7	10,2
23.00							6.085	1120	47,2	48,8	48,7							520	1120	11,2	11,2	10,8
24.00							-5.810	1120	44,1	47,5	48,7							-280	-1204	10,2	10,7	10,2

PT. PLN (PERSERO) UIW NTT
 Unit Pelaksana Pe mbangkitan Flores
 Unit Layanan Transmisi dan Gardu Induk Flores

Hari/Tanggal : Minggu, 30 Juli 2023																		
JAM	TAP	REGULATION PANEL 70/20 KV TRAF0 BAY									TRAFO 20 MVA 70/20 KV							
		KV			AMPERE sisi 70			TEG. 70			KW	KVAR	AMPERE sisi 20			TEMPERATUR		
		RS	ST	TR	R	S	T	R	S	T			R	S	T	OIL TEMP	LV WINDING TEMP	HV WINDING TEMP
00.00	1	22,0	22,0	21,8	49,0	50,0	50,2	73,1	73,0	72,7	6220,00	0,0	161,0	163,5	165,0			
01.00	1	22,0	22,0	21,8	48,4	48,5	48,7	73,0	73,0	72,6	5794,4	-6,7	149,2	152,5	154,7			
02.00	1	22,1	22,0	21,8	48,30	48,5	48,7	73,1	73,1	72,9	5068,0	0	145,7	148,8	150,0			
03.00	1	22,1	22,0	21,8	48,59	48,36	48,4	73,1	73,0	72,7	5504,0	0,0	141,2	144,5	146,4			
04.00	1	22,1	22,0	21,8	48,81	48,53	48,6	73,1	73,0	72,7	5746,0	-7,5	136,9	141,1	145,4			
05.00	1	22,1	22,0	21,8	48,61	48,64	48,7	73,1	73,0	72,7	5065,0	-9,1	146,9	145,2	146,5			
06.00	1	21,9	22,0	21,8	48,5	48,1	48,3	73,0	73,0	72,6	5756,0	-15,0	138,3	141,1	143,5			
07.00	1	21,9	22,0	21,8	48,8	48,4	48,4	73,0	73,0	72,1	5295,0	-29,9	130,5	133,9	136,6			
08.00	1	21,8	21,8	21,5	44,1	45,5	45,5	72,2	72,3	72,1	9221,0	6,07	142,0	143,0	143,0			
09.00	1	21,8	21,7	21,5	44,1	45,5	45,5	72,2	72,3	72,1	8572,0	8,21	142,0	143,0	143,0			
10.00	1	21,7	21,6	21,4	56,2	57,3	57,3	72,2	72,1	71,8	702,0	18,5	138,5	139,5	139,1			
11.00	1	21,7	21,6	21,4	56,2	57,3	57,3	72,2	72,1	71,8	702,0	18,5	138,5	139,5	139,1			
12.00	1	21,7	21,6	21,4	56,2	57,3	57,3	72,2	72,1	71,8	702,0	18,5	138,5	139,5	139,1			
13.00	1	21,8	21,7	21,5	45,5	45,5	45,5	72,2	72,3	72,0	562,0	9,53	144,9	151,1	152,2			
14.00	1	21,8	21,7	21,5	45,5	45,5	45,5	72,2	72,3	72,0	562,0	9,53	144,9	151,1	152,2			
15.00	1	21,8	21,7	21,5	48,0	48,0	48,0	72,4	72,2	71,9	6040,0	10,58	161,1	163,5	165,5			
16.00	1	21,7	21,7	21,4	57,1	57,1	57,1	72,3	72,2	71,9	6331,0	10,11	158,1	160,0	161,1			
17.00	1	21,7	21,6	21,3	48,7	48,6	48,5	72,1	72,1	71,7	6280,0	10,5	150,5	150,1	150,0			
18.00	1	21,5	21,5	21,2	63,4	64,5	64,5	72,3	72,3	71,1	9050,0	10,2	241,1	245,0	248,0			
19.00	1	21,5	21,5	21,2	63,4	64,5	64,5	72,3	72,3	71,1	10360,0	10,2	241,1	245,0	248,0			
20.00	1	21,6	21,7	21,5	77,1	78,0	78,0	72,8	72,8	71,5	9770,0	13,6	262,0	265,0	268,0			
21.00	1	21,7	21,7	21,5	68,6	68,2	68,2	72,0	72,0	71,7	8660,0	10,9	227,0	230,0	237,0			
22.00	1	21,8	21,8	21,6	61,1	61,8	61,8	72,4	72,4	72,1	7600,0	10,0	200,0	200,0	200,0			
23.00	1	21,9	21,9	21,7	62,5	62,8	62,8	72,3	72,6	72,3	6040,0	-	192,0	196,0	199,0			
24.00	1	22,0	22,0	21,8	48,0	48,0	48,0	72,0	72,0	72,0	6093,0	-	192,0	196,0	199,0			

LAMPIRAN 11
DATA HASIL DOWNLOAD TRENDING

Date : 31/07/2023

Site : Ende 70 kV Substation

Bay : Transmission Line 1

Time					
	Voltage	Current	Real Power	Apparent Power (Var)	Frequency
0:00:00	73.20	47.1	5.60	1.10	50.00
1:00:00	73.20	46.7	5.50	1.10	50.00
2:00:00	73.20	46.3	5.40	1.10	50.00
3:00:00	73.20	45.9	5.30	1.10	50.00
4:00:00	73.20	46.7	5.50	1.10	50.00
5:00:00	72.20	51.4	6.10	1.10	50.00
6:00:00	72.20	46.6	5.50	0.90	50.00
7:00:00	72.50	46.6	5.50	0.80	50.00
8:00:00	72.20	47.9	5.70	0.70	50.00
9:00:00	72.00	49.1	5.84	0.73	50.00
10:00:00	72.10	47.6	5.70	0.70	50.00
11:00:00	72.10	46.1	0.50	0.70	50.00
12:00:00	72.20	47.6	0.50	0.60	50.00
13:00:00	72.10	47.0	0.50	0.70	50.00
14:00:00	72.10	47.0	0.60	0.50	50.00
15:00:00	72.10	46.7	0.50	0.70	50.00
16:00:00	71.90	46.1	0.50	0.60	50.00
17:00:00	71.90	50.6	0.60	0.80	50.00
18:00:00	70.80	55.8	6.60	0.90	50.00
19:00:00	71.60	61.2	7.40	1.00	50.00
20:00:00	71.90	59.4	7.10	1.00	50.00
21:00:00	72.20	55.3	6.50	1.00	50.00
22:00:00	72.60	50.5	6.00	1.00	50.00
23:00:00	72.90	49.5	5.90	1.00	50.00
MAX	73.2	61.2	7.40	1.10	50.00
MIN	70.8	45.9	0.50	0.50	50.00
AVERAGE	72.3	49.4	4.37	0.87	50.00

Date : 31/07/2023
 Site : Ende 70 kV Substation
 Bay : Transformer

Time	Measurement			
	High Voltage	Medium Voltage	Current (MV)	Real Power (kW)
1:00:00	73.20	22.1	151.0	5664
2:00:00	73.20	22.1	146.0	5477
3:00:00	73.20	22.1	142.0	5327
4:00:00	73.20	22.1	138.0	5177
5:00:00	73.20	22.1	146.0	5477
6:00:00	72.20	21.8	176.0	6512
7:00:00	72.20	21.8	155.0	5735
8:00:00	72.50	21.8	148.0	5476
9:00:00	72.20	21.7	162.0	5967
10:00:00	72.00	21.7	175.4	6460
11:00:00	72.10	21.7	169.0	6225
12:00:00	72.10	21.6	159.0	5829
13:00:00	72.20	21.7	158.0	5820
14:00:00	72.10	21.6	154.0	5646
15:00:00	72.10	21.6	155.0	5683
16:00:00	72.10	21.7	150.0	5525
17:00:00	71.90	21.4	157.0	5703
18:00:00	71.90	21.9	157.0	5836
19:00:00	70.80	21.8	157.0	5809
20:00:00	71.60	21.4	157.0	5703
21:00:00	71.90	21.9	245.0	9107
22:00:00	72.20	21.8	217.0	8030
23:00:00	72.60	21.9	182.0	6765
24:00:00	72.90	22	171.0	6385
MAX	73.2	22.1	245.0	9,107
MIN	70.8	21.4	138.0	5,177
AVERAGE	72.3	21.8	163.6	6,056

SURAT KETERANGAN SURVEI

Yang bertandatangan di bawah ini :

Nama : Taruna Miftah Isnain
Perusahaan : PT PLN (Persero) Unit Layanan Transmisi dan Gardu Induk Flores (ULTG) Flores
Alamat : Jln. Gatot Subroto km 3, Kelurahan Mautapaga, Kecamatan Ende Timur,
Kabupaten Ende, Nusa Tenggara Timur

Dengan ini menyatakan bahwa :

Nama : Reza Bagus Nugrahardiyono
NIM : 2502103361
Jurusan : *Industrial Engineering*

Benar telah melakukan Survei Skripsi di bagian Operasi Gardu Induk 70 kV Ende – NTT, sejak tanggal 01 April 2023 di PT PLN (Persero) ULTG Flores dengan judul **"ANALISIS PERANCANGAN DAN IMPLEMENTASI *SUBSTATION AUTOMATION SYSTEM* PADA KEGIATAN OPERASIONAL GARDU INDUK 70 kV KONVENSIONAL DENGAN METODE *QUALITY FUNCTION DEPLOYMENT* DAN *USER CENTERED DESIGN*"** sebagai syarat untuk kelulusan Skripsi pada Jurusan Teknik Industri di Universitas Bina Nusantara.

Demikianlah surat pemberitahuan ini agar dapat dipergunakan sebaik-baiknya dan sebagaimana mestinya, atas perhatian dan kerjasamanya kami ucapkan terima kasih.

Ende, 12 April 2023
Manajer PT PLN (Persero) ULTG Flores

Taruna Miftah Isnain

RIWAYAT HIDUP

PERSONAL INFORMATION

Binusian ID	2502103361
Full Name	Reza Bagus Nugrahardiyono
E-Mail	reza.nugrahardiyono@binus.ac.id
Address	Jln. Payung Asri II / 1 RT 05 RW 01, Kelurahan Pudak Payung, Kecamatan Banyumanik, Kota Semarang
Phone Numbers	Home : 0247460214 Mobile : 081236116954
Gender	Male
Birth Place / Date	Semarang / 11 September 1995
Nationality	Indonesia
Marital Status	Single
Religion	Catholic

FORMAL EDUCATION

Aug 2013 – Aug 2016 Majoring in Electrical Engineering Major,
Department of Electrical Engineering,
Politeknik Negeri Semarang GPA : 3.63

INFORMAL EDUCATION

Jul 2020 Indonesian Stock Market Education

Jan 2023 IATKI Engineering Lecture of “Bi Directional
Inverter, DC Rectifier & Battery”

PROFESSIONAL CERTIFICATION

Mar 2026 Supervisor of Substation Maintenance
Certification

ORGANIZATION EXPERIENCE**WORKING EXPERIENCE**

Aug 2017 – Des 2020 Junior Engineer of Substation, Transimission
Line, and SCADA

Jan 2021 – present Supervisor of Operation and Maintenance